

THE ROLE OF MAHALLA AND NEIGHBORHOOD IN FORMING IDENTITY IN EDUCATION OF A CHILD

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Abstract. Currently, neighborhoods have become a very important body that works with the population. It is given the right to self-govern by a special law. Therefore, all the problems of the neighborhood and its residents will be solved there. Great educational work is carried out in the neighborhood. Based on the proverb "Seven neighbors to one child, parents" actively participate in the upbringing of children. The neighborhood is managed by a chairman and activists who are elected by the majority of the population and approved by the relevant district authorities. Discipline control is carried out by the inspector of internal affairs, volunteer guards. The importance and place of the neighborhood in the life of the population, which is of incomparable importance in the life of our society, and a phenomenon that has no parallel in the world experience, is increasing. After all, the neighborhood is "primary and incomparable space that teaches a person to live with society and educates in this spirit."

Keywords: neighborhoods, the population, self-govern, upbringing of children, chairman.

РОЛЬ МАХАЛЛИ И СОСЕДСТВА В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ИДЕНТИЧНОСТИ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ РЕБЕНКА

Аннотация. В настоящее время микрорайоны стали очень важным органом, работающим с населением. Специальным законом ему дано право на самоуправление. Поэтому все проблемы микрорайона и его жителей будут решаться там. В районе ведется большая просветительская работа. Исходя из поговорки «Семь соседей на одного ребенка, родители» активно участвуют в воспитании детей. Район управляется председателем и активистами, которые избираются большинством населения и утверждаются соответствующими районными властями. Контроль за дисциплиной осуществляют инспектор внутренних дел, добровольная дружина. Возрастает значение и место соседства в жизни населения, которое имеет ни с чем не сравнимое значение в жизни нашего общества, явление, не имеющее аналогов в мировом опыте. Ведь соседство – это «первичное и ни с чем не сравнимое пространство, которое учит человека жить с обществом и воспитывает в этом духе».

Ключевые слова: микрорайоны, население, самоуправление, воспитание детей, председатель.

INTRODUCTION

The Uzbek people are one of the peoples that stand out in the world for their spiritual values. The upbringing of children occupies an important place among the values of the Uzbek people. The appearance of teenagers outside the family is the focus of adults in the neighborhood who are interested in their activities. The fact that teenagers begin to grow up outside the family attracts the attention of adults who are interested in their activities in the neighborhood. Only among the peoples of Central Asia do we observe signs of indifference to children and adolescents, youthful morality, upbringing, self-esteem and prospects in society. This characteristic is one of the signs of the national identity of the Uzbek people. According to E. V.

Kovalevskaya, when a person - boys and girls - begins to realize his identity, the location of the surrounding information is of great importance for his consciousness. The scientist focuses on the psychological processes of self-realization of young people and the role of society and the events that take place in it. In fact, in the process of self-realization in adolescents, events and people around them have a great influence. In Uzbek folk pedagogy, views on the important role of neighborhood, neighbors and relatives - childbirth in the upbringing of adolescents are among the values transmitted to us from our ancestors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to the theoretical conclusions made by the Tajik scientist-teacher B. N. Karmyshova on the basis of scientific observations, samples of Tajik folk oral art serve as an important educational tool in the process of realizing the personality of students. In a sense, the student learns from the behavior and actions of the characters. Gets an idea of the ethnic symbols and values associated with his ancestors, the nation. The theoretical views of the scientist expressed the features of education common to neighboring peoples living in Central Asia. Although it is through folklore works, the main goal of pedagogy is to carry out the spiritual and moral education of young people in a perfect form. Here we considered it necessary to note that the Uzbek and Tajik peoples have common features in the upbringing of children, that these two peoples live apart from each other and do not have separate traditions. Although in the upbringing of children, both Tajiks and Uzbeks are guided by the problem of raising a person who is true to his national values, respects the traditions of his ancestors, respects the world and people. Although it was the representatives of these two peoples who, with their wise children, laid the cornerstone of the world scientific civilization since ancient times,

Observing the research of scientists from Tajikistan, we drew attention to the research of our colleague Mamadnosirova M.M. In his Ph.D. thesis, the scientist writes: "We are convinced that folk traditions, customs and rituals embody certain knowledge and skills in raising children and represent a great experience in raising the younger generation." The scientist's comments are correct. National values play an important role in the upbringing of the younger generation. In particular, it is appropriate to rely on national values in the formation of one's identity. What customs and traditions does the scientist mention? What are they made of? The answer to the question is the principle "Seven neighbor parents for one child" implemented in our microdistricts. The upbringing of children is considered one of the special and urgent tasks in the Neighborhood Institute. We are concerned that today's child is tomorrow's parent. Our people want our children to grow up under the influence of our national customs, values and traditions. Particular attention is paid to this issue in the process of mass education. When we say mass education, we mean that the same principle of education is important for many people.

RESULTS

Today, almost all the peoples of the world are looking for different ways to raise their children in the national spirit, to express their identity. The problem of self-consciousness attracts the attention of scientists of many peoples of the world is one of the problems. Indeed, today all of humanity recognizes that only if a person understands his identity, knows well who he is, he can be a person capable of giving positive results for his prospects and the bright future of his people. Therefore, one of the important tasks facing modern Uzbek pedagogy is the development of effective ways and methods for the formation of self-awareness in the upbringing of children.

In Uzbek society, there are two important factors for children to understand their identity:

1. Family. 2. Society.

In the family, parents, grandparents tell the child about his origin, the customs and traditions of his ancestors, about what he does well and what is bad.

DISCUSSION

Society is a factor that shapes the conscious life of a child and plays an important role in the process of learning about the world. The role of society in the upbringing of children is incomparable and of great importance. The role of society in the upbringing, life and destiny of a person is incomparable. educational and spiritual the force of society is so powerful that it dominates both the ascent of the individual to the highest peak and his absolute decline.

The structure of the society includes a microdistrict, an educational institution, cultural institutions, medical institutions. Whether we like it or not, our children, in one form or another, operate within the shell of society. This activity of the child extends not only to the process of upbringing, but also to the process of his education.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, the role of the neighborhood in the upbringing of our children, especially in ensuring originality in their minds, is extremely great. At the same time, we observe the education of our children in relationships with people, the development of their relationship with the environment, the formation of a spirit of respect and loyalty to our values.

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